

Household Environmental Swab Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	Sample Type	Sponge stick Swab (small)
6	Where was the sample collected from?	Front door Door handle (front door) Door handle (other) Curtain Fridge handle Cutlery / knife handle Chopping board Food preparation area Cooking equipment handle Rags / waster Toilet wall Table Chair Other (specify)
<p><i>You have completed data collection for this sample.</i></p> <p><i>Please complete 3 environmental samples per household where possible and 1 drain sample.</i></p>		
7	Staff signature	
8	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY